

Mixed ligand complex equilibria and coordination tendencies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with L-glutamine/L-citrulline and uracil

Divya Bartaria^a, Monika Singh and V. Krishna

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

^aUnited Institute of Technology, Naini, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : divya@united.ac.in

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Abstract : The speciation, plausible equilibrium and solution structural study of mixed-ligand complexes of L-glutamine/L-citrulline and uracil has been investigated by potentiometry involving Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} metal ions. The overall stability constants of ternary complexes have been determined in biologically relevant conditions and at ionic strength of 0.1 M NaNO₃. The models containing different numbers of species were refined by using the computer program SCOGS. The stability constants and complexation equilibria for the best-fit chemical models were arrived at based on statistical parameters. The trend in variation of stability constants of 1 : 1 : 1 L-Gln/L-Cit(A) : M^{II} : uracil(B) evidenced as ACu^{II}B > AZn^{II}B > ANi^{II}B > ACo^{II}B; is attributed to the electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

Keywords : Glutamine, uracil, citrulline, mixed ligand complex.

Introduction

Ternary complexes¹ are known to play a very important role in various biological processes including detoxification of toxic cations. The interaction² of metal ions with amino acids, peptides and nucleobases is of great significance because of their relevance to the essential, medicinal and toxic bioactivity of metal centers.

L-Glutamine is a basic amino acid and an amide of glutamic acid, whose side-chain is an amide formed by replacing the side-chain hydroxyl of glutamic acid with an amine functional group. The study of glutamine (Gln) complexes may provide further evidence about the nature of the peptide complexes. L-Citrulline (Cit) is a non-essential amino acid and is also found to support detoxification pathways. Attractive ligand-ligand interactions favor the formation of mixed ligand complexes, giving rise to ligand selectivity or a preferred combination of ligands around a metal ion^{3,4}. In humans, glutamine (Gln) is the most abundant amino acid in the extra and intracellular compartments, contributing to greater than 50% of the free amino acid pool in muscle^{5,6}. Glutamine is involved in many metabolic and synthetic biochemical processes. It is the preferred energy source for the rapidly prolifera-

ting cells of the gastrointestinal tract and the immune system⁷⁻¹⁰. Regulatory functions of glutamine in muscle protein turnover have been suggested and the cellular hydration state was proposed to represent the link connecting muscle protein turnover to free glutamine concentrations^{11,12}. Studies have indicated that glutamine supplementation is potentially effective in preventing side effects for patients receiving high dose chemotherapy and bone marrow transplantation¹³. Cobalt, nickel and copper are essential trace elements and are vital. Glutamine is synthesized by the liver. So there is every likely hood for their interaction in the liver. Hence these three metals are taken as representative systems to essential trace metals. Cobalt is essential for the production of the red blood cells and cobalamin (B12 form) acts as the substrate for the enzymatic reaction that yields the active coenzyme derivatives of cyanocobalamin and aqua cobalamin¹⁴. Nickel is present in enzymes like urease¹⁵ and any variation in its concentration leads to metabolic disorders. Copper is an essential trace nutrient to all higher plant and animal life. It is found primarily in the blood stream, as a co-factor in various enzymes and in copper-based pigments. Most of the speciation studies are performed in aqueous media under conditions comparable to those ex-

isting in physiological systems. These are taken as models for the systems existing in biofluids and natural water.

Taking these facts into consideration we report herein the stability constants of ternary complexes of L-glutamine and L-citrulline using Irving-Rossotti¹⁶ pH-titration technique in biologically relevant conditions. Solution studies involving potentiometry and SCOGS¹⁷ computer program has lead us to assess and examine the stability constant, complexation equilibria, speciation curves and coordination tendencies of 1 : 1 : 1 L-gln/L-cit(A) : M(II) : uracil(B) complexes with respect to the nature and structure of the ligands as well as nature of metal ions. The results of the present work basically provide a quantitative and structural description.

Experimental

Stock solutions (0.01 M) of L-glutamine and L-citrulline were prepared by constant stirring in double distilled water. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared and standardized by EDTA titration¹⁸. Solutions of NaOH and HNO₃ were prepared in carbon dioxide free double distilled water and standardized against standard oxalic acid as usual. A 0.01 M solution of uracil was prepared by dissolving it into one equivalent of alkali (NaOH).

The other experimental details have been described elsewhere¹⁹. The ionic strength of all mixture solutions was kept 0.1 M NaNO₃. The free acid concentration was kept 0.02 M in each case. The following sets of solutions were prepared keeping the total volume 50 ml in each case. The molar ratio of primary ligand, metal and the secondary ligand undertaken was kept 1 : 1 : 1.

Set-I : HNO₃ (0.02 M)

Set-II(a) : HNO₃ (0.02 M) + A (0.01 M)

Set-II(b) : HNO₃ (0.02 M) + B (0.01 M)

Set-III(a) : HNO₃ (0.02 M) + A (0.01 M)
+ M^{II}(NO₃)₂ (0.01 M)

Set-III(b) : HNO₃ (0.02 M) + B (0.01 M)
+ M^{II}(NO₃)₂ (0.01 M)

Set-IV : HNO₃ (0.02 M) + A (0.01 M)
+ M^{II}(NO₃)₂ (0.01 M) + B (0.01 M)

where M^{II} = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II}, A = L-glutamine (Gln)/L-citrulline (Cit) and B = uracil.

Results and discussion

At physiological conditions, both the ligands exist as H₂L⁻ ions, with deprotonated basic functions. From the chemical point of view, glutamine (Gln), is optically active and includes side chain groups likely to form a chelate ring with a metal ion bound at the amino nitrogen. It includes an amide function at its respective β and γ positions and coordinates in a glycine-like manner. The refined values of acid dissociation constants are listed in Table 1. The overall stability constant for ternary complexes formed by the interaction between metal ions M^{II}

Table 1. Stability constants of binary and ternary complexes of L-glutamine/L-citrulline (A) and uracil (B) with different metal ions in aqueous solution at 37 ± 1 °C, I = 0.1 M NaNO₃

(i) Proton-ligand formation constants (log β _{0qrs}) :				
	log β ₀₁₀₋₁	log β ₀₁₀₋₂		
L-Glutamine (Gln) (A)	9.01	11.18		
L-Citrulline (Cit) (A)	11.84	9.41		
(ii) Metal-ligand constants (log β ₁₁₀₀ /log β ₁₀₁₀) : Binary systems				
	Cu	Zn	Ni	Co
M ^{II} -Gln	7.75	4.62	5.56	4.40
M ^{II} -Cit	7.92	4.13	5.10	3.94
M ^{II} -uracil	8.25	6.61	6.80	6.28
(iii) Metal-ligand constants (log β ₁₁₁₀) : Ternary systems				
	Cu	Zn	Ni	Co
M ^{II} -Gln-uracil	12.52	10.52	10.35	9.16
M ^{II} -Cit-uracil	12.32	10.00	9.95	9.08

with ligands A and B is expressed as given below (charges are omitted for clarity) :

$$\begin{aligned}
 & pM + qA + rB + sOH \rightleftharpoons M_pA_qB_r(OH)_s \\
 & \beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[M_pA_qB_r(OH)_s]}{[M]^p[A]^q[B]^r[(OH)]^s}
 \end{aligned}$$

where, integer s is positive for a hydroxo species, negative for a protonated species and zero for a neutral species. The evaluation and refinement of stability constant²⁰ of the complexes formed have been done and species distribution curves were obtained by plotting % concentration vs pH. Ionic product of water (K_w) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the experimental conditions were obtained from the literature²¹.

Comparing the speciation curves of systems containing glutamine as a primary ligand, followings sets in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio are formed : Gln-Cu^{II}-B > Gln-Zn^{II}-B > Gln-Ni^{II}-B > Gln-Co^{II}-B and these mixed ligand ternary complexes are the dominant species in the pH range > 8.0 and their maxima are found to be 80.9% (at pH ~ 9.06), 78.9% (at pH ~ 9.3), 77.4% (at pH ~ 9.73) and 64.1% (at pH ~ 9.75) respectively. Considering protonation constants of ligands and hydrolytic constants of metal M^{II}, following species have been found to exist in all the systems : M²⁺, H₂A, HA, BH, M(OH)₂, M(OH)⁺, MA, MB and MAB. All the protonated species are found to follow a declining pattern of their concentrations within the pH range ~2.9–10.0, indicating their involvement in complexation. The hydroxo species are also found to exist as the buffer region corresponding to the metal ligand formation equilibria are found to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of metal ions in solution.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of glutamine.

Fig. 2. Chemical structure of citrulline.

Formally, glutamine contains three electron-donating centres. However, its amide group, like that of asparagine, dissociates at a pH near the limit of the ionic product of water and the dissociation cannot be detected in aqueous solution²². Thus, the only measurable effect of adding a -CH₂ group to the asparagine skeleton in respect of the proton interactions of these two amino acids is the

increased stability of the protonated forms of the glycine-like donors of glutamine. This effect, almost totally entropic in nature, has been attributed to the larger perturbation brought about by the proton approach in the solvation shell of the more hydrophobic glutamine molecule²³. For metal complexation, attempts have been made to characterize a possible participation of the amide group in the coordination of several metal ions²⁴. However, given the unfavourable size of the chelate ring potentially involved, glutamine displays only a very weak tridentate capability with cobalt(II) and nickel(II)²⁴ and exclusively behaves as a bidentate ligand with copper(II)²². This is in line with the fact that the formation of copper(II)-glutamine complexes is not accompanied by any stereoselective effect²⁵. In a few mixed-ligand complexes involving amino acid, tridentate coordination of glutamine has been reported. The complexes are formed by coordination of the amino and carboxyl groups. Upon deprotonation of the amide group, the coordination sites would switch from carbonyl oxygen to amide nitrogen. Such changes in coordination centers are well documented²⁶.

Since citrulline is a diacid and at alkaline pH, both the carboxylic and amine groups can act as Lewis donors, which means they can complex metallic cations. Uracil, a pyrimidine undergoes keto enol tautomeric shifts because of its resonance structure due to -NH₂ and -OH substituents. The keto tautomer is referred as the lactam structure while the enol tautomer is referred as lactim structure (Fig. 3).

On the basis of UV measurements in aqueous solution, uracil exists primarily in the diketo form where as in alkaline solution; it exists as approximately 1 : 1 mixture of the two possible deprotonated forms. Two overlapping absorption bands with max 260 and 284 nm have been reported for proton ionization from neutral uracil with a conclusion that protons ionize simultaneously from both N₁H and N₃H groups.

Fig. 3

Ultraviolet and ultrasonic absorption studies^{27,28} indicate that U and T primarily exit in the lactam form in an aqueous solution. However, in the alkaline solution two ionizations were detected that of the α -hydroxyl group characterized by pK_1 and that of the γ -hydroxyl group for pK_2 . The pK_a values for T are slightly higher which is perhaps due to the presence of $-CH_3$ group at 5 positions. The possible stepwise ionizations involved in the cases of U and T are summarized below (Fig. 4) :

Speciation curves in Fig. 5 suggest the following complex equilibria (omitting the charges) :

Speciation curves in Fig. 6 suggest the following complex equilibria (omitting the charges) :

Major equilibria :

Minor equilibria :

A comparison of stability with respect to the $\log \beta$ values obtained through SCOGS shows following order of the ternary complexes : Cit-Cu^{II}-B > Cit-Zn^{II}-B > Cit-Ni^{II}-B > Cit-Co^{II}-B.

As is evident, the above sequence is in conformity with the Irving-Williams order. The additional high stability of the Cu^{II} complex is attributed to the unique elec-

Fig. 4. (R = H, uracil; R = CH₃, thymine)

Fig. 5. Distribution curves of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-glutamine (A)-uracil (B) system : (1) Cu²⁺, (2) AH₂, (3) AH, (4) BH, (5) Cu(OH)₂, (6) Cu^{II}-A, (7) Cu^{II}-B, (8) Cu^{II}-A-B.

Fig. 6. Distribution curves of 1 : 1 : 1 Ni^{II} -citrulline (A)-uracil (B) system : (1) Ni^{2+} , (2) AH_2 , (3) AH , (4) BH , (5) $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$, (6) $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})^+$, (7) $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-A}$, (8) $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-B}$, (9) $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-A-B}$.

tronic configuration ($3d^9$) of Cu^{II} ion which is capable of additional stabilization due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The extra stability of the ternary complexes is due to the interactions outside the coordination sphere. This may sometimes be due to the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, charge neutralization, chelate effect, stacking interactions and a similar stabilizing effect may likewise be exerted by the electrostatic interactions between non-coordinated, charged groups of the ligands. Sakuri *et al.*²⁹ carried out extensive studies to establish the laws governing interactions of this nature.

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